

Open-Source Modeling of Syngas Production from Biomass: A Code-Driven Approach

Daniel Chuquín-Vasco,* Vanesa G. Lo-Iacono-Ferreira,* and Juan I. Torregrosa-López

Cite This: *ACS Eng. Au* 2025, 5, 670–681

Read Online

ACCESS |

Metrics & More

Article Recommendations

Supporting Information

ABSTRACT: Plasma gasification is a promising thermochemical technology for converting municipal solid waste into syngas with a reduced environmental impact. However, research in this field is limited to the use of black-box software, which impedes methodological innovation and is key to advanced research into gasification processes. This study proposes a fully open-source and modular simulation model for plasma gasification of municipal solid waste developed in Python. The model consists of three interconnected modules: (1) decomposition of biomass into its elemental constituents, (2) simulation of the plasma gasifying stream, and (3) kinetic modeling of chemical reactions in a plug-flow reactor (PFR). Thermodynamic properties and reaction kinetics are implemented by using scientific Python libraries (Pyromat, CoolProp, Pint, NumPy, and SciPy). The model was validated against commercial Aspen Plus simulations by using experimental data. It achieved low mean absolute percentage errors (MAPEs) of 1.04% for Modules 1 and 2 and 14.19% for the reactor model. The predicted syngas composition at the reactor outlet was 44.3% hydrogen, 18.2% carbon monoxide, 12.7% carbon dioxide, and 14.8% water vapor (on a molar basis). Sensitivity analysis showed that increasing the air equivalence ratio from 0.04 to 0.16 reduced hydrogen and carbon monoxide concentrations by 25.7% and 42.4%, respectively. The optimal steam-to-fuel ratio was 0.08, which maximized hydrogen production to up to 45.5%. This open-source framework enables reproducible research and can be expanded with optimization algorithms and environmental or techno-economic assessments in future studies.

KEYWORDS: biomass, gasification, modeling, open-source, plasma, syngas

The model was validated against commercial Aspen Plus simulations by using experimental data. It achieved low mean absolute percentage errors (MAPEs) of 1.04% for Modules 1 and 2 and 14.19% for the reactor model. The predicted syngas composition at the reactor outlet was 44.3% hydrogen, 18.2% carbon monoxide, 12.7% carbon dioxide, and 14.8% water vapor (on a molar basis). Sensitivity analysis showed that increasing the air equivalence ratio from 0.04 to 0.16 reduced hydrogen and carbon monoxide concentrations by 25.7% and 42.4%, respectively. The optimal steam-to-fuel ratio was 0.08, which maximized hydrogen production to up to 45.5%. This open-source framework enables reproducible research and can be expanded with optimization algorithms and environmental or techno-economic assessments in future studies.

1. INTRODUCTION

Open-source software (OSS) is widely used by researchers to promote the development and distribution of innovative discoveries and scientific advancements.¹ The application of OSS tools promotes the active participation of researchers and the scientific community. Critical analysis of the source codes allows faster identification of possible errors and allows the adaptation and distribution of the codes, thus promoting their continuous improvement.² OSS can be freely shared, modified, and reused, which plays an important role in software development.³ Today, the use of open source has successfully transformed technologies in the industrial sector in such a way that it has encouraged accelerated code development, intending to minimize costs and guarantee the stability and security of the process.³ OSS can potentially transform industrial sectors; however, its application has not been widespread in the energy sector.⁴ OSS is emerging as an alternative to proprietary solutions for planning, implementation, and maintenance of localized access to clean renewable electricity.⁵ In this sense, it is vital to consider the development of open-source code capable of representing the behavior of an energy system that includes integrating renewable energy,

minimizing environmental impact, and maximizing energy efficiency.⁶

Biomass has emerged as a powerful renewable energy source, gaining traction for its ability to produce energy from eco-friendly practices like reforestation, crop rotation, and waste-to-energy recovery.⁷ Biomass gasification is a waste thermal treatment technique developed to reduce greenhouse gas emissions compared to conventional techniques, such as burning fossil fuels. Its energy use contributes to the transition toward more sustainable energy systems with a lower carbon footprint.⁸ By 2035, biomass is forecast to contribute 10% of global energy demand, and by 2050, 27% of global transportation fuels are projected to come from biofuels generated by gasification processes.⁹ Biomass-based energy (bioenergy) is highly adaptable and well-suited for integration into sustainable industrial operations. Producing and utilizing biofuels through

Received: June 11, 2025

Revised: August 28, 2025

Accepted: August 29, 2025

Published: September 7, 2025

gasification plays a crucial role in reducing carbon emissions from sectors and manufacturing processes that are challenging to decarbonize.¹⁰

Syngas is one of the main products of biomass gasification and is considered a viable alternative to replace natural gas.¹¹ The primary components of syngas include carbon monoxide (CO), hydrogen (H₂), and small amounts of methane (CH₄), carbon dioxide (CO₂), and tars.⁷ However, the syngas also contains large quantities of impurities, such as dust, soot, ashes, and vapors, which can lead to issues like fouling and plugging of downstream equipment.¹² Syngas generates heat and electricity, produces biofuels, and creates chemical products.¹³ Approximately 50% of the syngas produced worldwide is used to manufacture ammonia, while about 25% is utilized to obtain hydrogen.¹⁴ The remaining syngas can be converted into other valuable compounds, such as methanol or byproducts of the Fischer–Tropsch (FT) process.¹³

Plasma gasification is currently one of the most widely used methods for solid waste treatment because it enhances the reaction rate¹⁵ and promotes cleaner syngas production compared to traditional gasification technologies.¹⁶ Plasma gasification involves the conversion of complex hydrocarbons into synthesis gas at extremely high temperatures, exceeding 4000 °C to break down waste into its basic molecular components and generate syngas.¹⁷ The energy-rich synthesis gas (primarily composed of hydrogen and carbon monoxide) is cooled and purified before being converted into ethanol, hydrogen, or natural gas or used as fuel for gas turbines or combustion engines to generate electricity.¹⁸ Plasma gasification can be classified into three categories: direct current (DC) plasma, microwave (MW) plasma, and radio frequency (RF) plasma.¹⁹ Plasma gasification generates approximately 816 kWh per ton of municipal solid waste (MSW), exceeding 685 kWh per ton of conventional gasification. Therefore, it can be considered the most efficient form of thermal gasification.²⁰

The development of gasification models from experimental data and gasifiers installed in plants is currently trending, primarily due to their scalability for industrial processes. Advanced simulation tools have been developed to analyze the waste-to-energy process, enhancing the design and efficiency of plasma gasification systems,²¹ for example, a plasma gasification model of medical waste with nitrogen, evaluating optimal conditions and feasibility,²² a model of municipal solid waste (MSW) to assess syngas quality and process feasibility where the air showed optimal performance with high syngas yield and estimated costs of \$125.5 M (capital) and \$9.8M/year (operation),²³ a steady-state model of an integrated plasma gasification combined-cycle power plant to analyze how plasma temperature affects power production,²⁴ a multistage gasification system for producing a syngas with a low tar content,²⁵ and syngas production from MSW gasification in a Bubbling Fluidized Bed.²⁶

Despite the progress made with commercial platforms such as Aspen Plus, the most widely used tool for modeling and optimizing gasification processes,^{27,28} these closed-source solutions impose significant restrictions. Their high licensing costs and the opacity of their internal structures severely limit access to researchers, hindering innovation and academic collaboration. This lack of transparency complicates independent validation, algorithm modification, and adaptation to new operational conditions, which are critical for continuous advancement in gasification process optimization. Furthermore, most gasification models proposed in Aspen consider

thermodynamic equilibrium, as seen in studies by Cvetinović et al.,²⁹ who conducted a techno-economic assessment of plasma gasification, and by Dossow et al.,³⁰ who evaluated biomass conversion using plasma gasification. These models are helpful for general analyses but do not consider reaction kinetics, which are important for making accurate predictions of the syngas composition under realistic conditions. This limitation is particularly relevant, as Batista et al.³¹ determined that kinetic models are more accurate than equilibrium models, especially under variable conditions, and recent studies, such as those by Angikath et al.,³² demonstrate that free radical modeling reveals complex interactions in plastic mixtures that are unattainable with simplified models.

In response, open-source tools such as Python³³ are emerging as an alternative that promotes transparency, reproducibility, and academic collaboration. The challenge in modeling gasification processes is to create models that allow the identification of optimal parameters while minimizing cost and maximizing the production of good-quality syngas.³⁴ The development of open, modular models is therefore essential to advance the design of cost-effective and efficient gasification systems.³⁵ Oladokun et al.³⁶ introduced the gasification model in Python; however, for simplicity, the model is based solely on thermodynamic equilibrium, lacking kinetic mechanisms and not accounting for reactor dynamics such as those represented in plug flow reactors (PFRs).

The use of open-source software, unlike commercial software, allows users to access the source code for complex gasification systems, which involve chemical reactions, mass and energy transfer, air-fuel ratio analysis, and plasma flow, among other processes. Open source promotes open science and continuous process improvement and facilitates adaptation, scalability, and scientific validation based on the operating parameters of the gasification system and the characteristics of the biomass. Modular approaches using open-source code enable efficient solutions to systems of multiphysics equations without the need for manual integration.³⁷ Modularization in a plasma gasification system enables the prediction of major syngas components based on the kinetics of oxidation and reduction reactions of heterogeneous biomass components. Furthermore, open source promotes reproducibility and accelerates the development of more sustainable solutions. Therefore, these tools represent a strategic alternative for developing practical solutions that optimize the gasification process, improve gasifier performance, minimize environmental impacts, and maximize the amount of heat that can be generated from syngas.

We hypothesize that a modular, open-source model can accurately simulate plasma gasification of municipal solid waste using the reaction kinetics in plug-flow reactors. Current work focuses on model development and validation to enable future optimization analysis of syngas production and process efficiency. To close this research gap, in this study, we propose developing an open-source plasma gasification model to represent the behavior and prediction of a municipal solid waste gasification process. Unlike most studies that rely on equilibrium models using Aspen Plus (closed-source software),³⁸ our model allows for transparency, reproducibility, and full customization.

Our model is one of the first open-source models to simulate plasma gasification processes using a plug-flow reactor with kinetic parameters considering the major gasification reactions and their corresponding kinetics rates. The PFR has hydro-

Figure 1. Modules of the municipal solid waste (MSW) gasification system.

dynamic behavior similar to that of industrial gasifiers and thus allows for accurate prediction of concentration profiles and thermochemical transformations.³⁹ The main contributions of this work are:

Development of a modular, fully open-source model in Jupyter Notebook⁴⁰ using key Python libraries³³ for simulating biomass gasification in a PFR.

Integration of kinetic mechanisms for significant heterogeneous and homogeneous gasification reactions, enabling a realistic prediction of syngas composition.

Implementation of three independent modules for biomass decomposition into its elemental components (C, H, O, N, S, H₂O, ash) based on its proximate and ultimate analysis (MODULE 1), plasma stream modeling and thermal mixing (MODULE 2), and reaction kinetics in the reactor (MODULE 3).

Validation of the model against literature data from Aspen Plus to demonstrate its accuracy and potential for research and education.

Sensitivity analysis of the equivalence ratio (ER) and steam-fuel ratio (SFR) to analyze the hydrogen production and carbon conversion.

Promotion of open science by providing accessible tools for sustainable waste-to-energy process design.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Description of the Programming Model

This work developed a computational module to produce syngas from biomass coming from municipal solid waste (MSW) using Python³³ programming language, an open-source software. OSS invites researchers to critique the code, understand the process's mathematical principles, parameters, and hypotheses, and modify it as needed.¹ The modeling was designed in three (3) modules (Figure 1), Biomass Decomposition (MOD-1); Gasifying Agent (MOD-2); and Gasification Reactor (MOD-3), to adequately describe the

thermochemical conversion of biomass into syngas using typical operating ranges and evaluate the traceability of the calculations.

The model was implemented in Jupyter Notebook version 7.2.2⁴⁰ using NumPy⁴¹ and SciPy⁴² to resolve and calculate differential equations and Pyromat⁴³ and CoolProp⁴⁴ to determine the thermodynamic properties of the species involved in the gasification process. Additionally, the Pint⁴⁵ tool was used to properly manage the physical units of the parameters employed in the code.

The implemented modules allow for the simulation of syngas production from biomass derived from municipal solid waste through the detailed calculation of the mass and energy balances. This approach takes into account the evaluation of the results from four distinct substreams in the gasification process, Total Stream (Considers conventional, solid, and nonconventional elements), Mixed Substream (only conventional elements), Solid Substream (C in solid form), and Non-Conventional Substream (Biomass and ash), in such a way that what happens with the conventional elements (H, O, N, among others), the solid element (C in the form of graphite), and the nonconventional elements is better understood.

Additionally, the model utilizes a mixture of air and steam, termed plasma, as the gasifying agent to assess its impact on the final composition of the syngas. The model's accuracy was validated by comparing it with a previous study conducted by Nemmour et al.¹⁸ using Aspen Plus, which is a closed-source and commercial software tool.

The following section briefly describes the modules that simulate the MSW gasification process. Each module focuses on a specific step from biomass characterization to modeling of the reactions within the reactor.

2.1.1. MOD-1. This module aims to transform the heterogeneous biomass stream into a mixture of conventional elements using a yield distribution based on elemental and proximate analyses of MSW. This determines the dry-basis composition of solid carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen, sulfur, water, and ash. This decomposition is helpful because there are no thermodynamic models to directly calculate the thermodynamic properties of the heterogeneous biomass stream prior to entering the gasification reactor.⁴⁶

2.1.2. MOD-2. This module facilitates the mixing of air and steam with preheating at elevated temperatures before it enters the

Table 1. MSW Range Composition

Proximate analysis (wt %)				Ultimate analysis (wt %)			ref
Moisture	Volatile matter	Fixed carbon	Ash	C	H	O	
7.7–60.56	57–83.96	3.6–85.02	2.53–79.23	17.85–55.23	2.74–9.38	6.9–40.55	18, 48–50

Table 2. Oxidation Reactions and Kinetics Rates

Reaction name	Reaction type	Reaction	Kinetic rate (kmol/m ³ ·s)	Reference
Carbon Oxidation	Heterogeneous	1.25C + O ₂ → 0.5CO + 0.75CO ₂	$3.7 \times 10^{10} e^{-1.5 \times 10^5 / RT} \times [O][C]$	52
Partial Methane Oxidation	Homogeneous	CH ₄ + 0.5O ₂ → CO + 2H ₂	$1.58 \times 10^{12} e^{-2.02 \times 10^5 / RT} \times [CH_4]^{0.7} [O_2]^{0.8}$	53
Hydrogen Oxidation	Homogeneous	H ₂ + 0.5O ₂ → H ₂ O	$1.08 \times 10^7 e^{-1.08 \times 10^4 / RT} \times [H_2][O_2]$	53
CO Oxidation	Homogeneous	CO + 0.5O ₂ → CO ₂	$1.78 \times 10^7 e^{-1.8 \times 10^5 / RT} \times [CO][O_2]^{0.25}$	54

Table 3. Reduction Reactions and Kinetics Rates

Reaction name	Reaction type	Reaction	Kinetic rate (kmol/m ³ ·s)	Reference
Water/Gas	Heterogeneous	C + H ₂ O → CO + H ₂	$8 \times 10^{-3} e^{-4.99 \times 10^4 / RT} \times [C][H_2O]$	55
Boudouard	Heterogeneous	C + CO ₂ → 2CO	$4.4 \times 10^4 e^{-1.62 \times 10^5 / RT} \times [C][CO_2]$	56
H ₂ Gasification	Heterogeneous	C + 2H ₂ → CH ₄	$1 \times 10^{-4} e^{-1.0363 \times 10^5 / RT} \times [C][H_2O]$	57
Water/Gas Shift	Homogeneous	CO + H ₂ O → CO ₂ + H ₂	$1.35 \times 10^5 e^{-102400 / RT} \times [CO][H_2O]$	58
CO ₂ Reduction	Homogeneous	CO ₂ + H ₂ → CO + H ₂ O	$1.2 \times 10^{10} e^{-318000 / RT} \times [CO_2][H_2]^{0.5}$	59
Methane Reforming	Homogeneous	CH ₄ + H ₂ O → CO + 3H ₂	$3.0 \times 10^{13} e^{-1.25 \times 10^5 / RT} \times [CO_2][H_2O]^{0.5}$	24

gasification reactor, which serves as a gasifying agent, known as plasma. The goal is to enhance the thermochemical conversion of municipal solid waste (MSW) into syngas.

It is important to clarify that, although the term “plasma” is used throughout this work, the model does not explicitly simulate the physics of plasma or ionized species. Instead, “plasma” refers to the high-temperature air-steam mixture produced by a plasma torch, and its effects are captured through elevated temperatures and kinetic modeling. This approach allows for accurate prediction of concentration profiles and thermochemical transformations, which more closely resemble the in situ behavior of industrial gasifiers.²⁴

2.1.3. MOD-3. This module simulates the primary reactions that occur in an MSW gasification reactor. It incorporates heterogeneous reactions, such as carbon oxidation and methanation, as well as homogeneous reactions, including the reduction of carbon monoxide (CO) and carbon dioxide (CO₂). The model facilitates calculation of the production of hydrogen (H₂), carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), and methane (CH₄). The reaction kinetics are based on the Arrhenius equation,⁴⁷ employing pre-exponential factors, activation energies, and reaction orders sourced from existing literature.

2.2. Biomass Characterization

Proximate and elemental analysis identifies the main components of biomass: moisture, volatile matter, fixed carbon, and ash, which directly influence the process's reactivity and performance. Table 1 details the typical percentages of biomass from municipal waste used in the gasification process modeling.

The variation in MSW composition shown in Table 1 demonstrates the heterogeneity of MSW used in gasification processes and reported in the literature. In our particular case, for model validation purposes, we used the values in Table 4, based on the study conducted by Nemmour et al.,¹⁸ which serves as the baseline for all calculations in this work. These values are within the typical variation range of the MSW.

2.3. Reactions Considered in the Model

Once the biomass has been decomposed in MOD-1 into its elemental components, carbon, in the form of graphite, and conventional components such as H, CH₄, CO, and CO₂ react with the surrounding gases to produce gaseous compounds. At the same time, the ash behaves as an inert matter and does not undergo any reaction.

The reaction rate was modeled using kinetics by the Power Law⁵¹ as a function of temperature and the molar concentrations of the reactants (eq 1).

$$r = k(T) \times \prod_i c_i^{n_i} \quad (1)$$

where r is the reaction rate (mol/m³ s), c_i is the molar concentration of species i (kmol/m³), and n_i is the partial order of reaction with respect to each reacting species.

The kinetic constant $k(T)$ varies with temperature (eq 2) according to the Arrhenius expression:⁴⁷

$$k(T) = A \times e^{-\left(\frac{E}{RT}\right)} \quad (2)$$

where A represents the pre-exponential factor, E is the activation energy (kJ/kmol), R is the universal gas constant (8.314 J/mol K), and T is the absolute temperature (K). This structure allows the kinetic expression to be adapted to different reactions by adjusting only the values of A and E and the partial orders n_i for each reactant species. Table 2 and Table 3 detail the oxidation and reduction reactions and kinetics considered in the gasification process.

The reactions and kinetic parameters employed in this study were extracted from recent literature focused on the gasification of lignocellulosic biomass and organic waste (e.g., macadamia nutshells, microalgae, chili straw, MSW), all of which are compositionally similar to the dry organic fraction of MSW. These parameters are valid for high-temperature gasification processes (typically in the range of 1000–1600 K). In our model, the reactor operates at 1523.15 K, representing the average postmixing temperature resulting from the interaction between the plasma jet and the biomass

Table 4. Biomass Composition^a

Proximate analysis (wt %)				Ultimate analysis (wt %)					
Moisture	Volatile matter	Fixed carbon	Ash	C	H	O	N	S	Cl
20	75.96	10.23	13.81	48.23	6.37	28.48	1.22	0.76	1.13

^aSource: Ref 18.

feedstock. Although plasma torches can reach ultrahigh temperatures (>3000 K), this peak is highly localized and rapidly moderated by mixing effects and heat transfer losses. Therefore, the use of conventional kinetic expressions remains appropriate within the modeled temperature conditions. This approach is consistent with studies such as Nemmour et al.,¹⁸ which apply conventional kinetics under similar plasma gasification regimes. Future work will include tuning and calibration of the kinetic parameters using optimization algorithms or plasma-specific reaction mechanisms to better account for the inherent variability in MSW composition and the distinctive thermochemical environment of plasma-assisted systems.

2.4. Estimation of Thermodynamic and Physical Properties

The developed modules require the application of thermodynamic methods capable of accurately representing the properties of the components involved in the gasification process. These properties are essential for formulating and resolving mass and energy balances and subsequently predicting the evolution of syngas composition in the system's substreams. The methodologies implemented for each substream are described below. The equations explained in detail for estimating thermodynamic properties are detailed in SI: Appendix I.

2.5. Operating Conditions

For validation purposes, we adapted the plasma gasification model based on Nemmour et al.,¹⁸ considering the proximal and elemental analysis of MSW detailed in Table 4. The conditions of the streams used in the model are specified in Table 5, where MSW2 represents the biomass stream entering the decomposition process in MOD-1. The steam and air streams serve as gasifying agents, which are mixed to create plasma.

Table 5. Stream Parameters of MOD-1 and MOD-2^a

Description	MSW2	Air	Steam
Temperature (K)	393.15	298.15	1273.15
Pressure (atm)	1	1	1
Mass flow (kg/s)	0.005692	0.0017	0.001708
Mole fraction O ₂	0	0.188	0
Mole fraction N ₂	0	0.8112	0
Mole fraction H ₂ O	0		1

^aSource: Ref 18.

In this work, the plasma torch is represented as a pseudostream composed of air and steam at 4273.15 K, introduced as an energy carrier rather than as a realistic plasma arc (MOD-2). This simplification focuses on simulating the thermal energy transferred by plasma to the feedstock rather than the detailed plasma physics. Similar approaches are used in previous literature, including Nemmour et al.,¹⁸ where plasma is modeled as a high-temperature stream delivering heat to the gasification zone.

The reactor employed in this process was a plug-flow reactor (PFR) that operated under atmospheric, adiabatic, and steady-state conditions (MOD-3). These assumptions are commonly adopted in high-temperature gasification studies,^{57,58,60} especially in plasma-assisted configurations where the thermal energy is concentrated in the plasma generation zone and the reactor is thermally insulated to minimize heat losses. The steady-state approximation represents a continuous and stable operation regime consistent with the boundary conditions of our simulation, although these simplifications are

appropriate for validation purposes and for capturing the average behavior of the system.

The operating parameters of the reactor are summarized in Table 6. The steady-state assumption allows the model to solve the mass and

Table 6. Plug Flow Reactor Parameter

Description	Value	Reference
Temperature (K)	1523.15	18, 59
Pressure (atm)	1	18, 59
Diameter (m)	0.49	18, 59
Length (m)	1.2	18, 59

energy conservation equations, enabling an accurate estimation of the compositional evolution of the primary species in the synthesis gas.

The data presented in Tables 5 and 6 were directly adopted from the experimental and simulation study by Nemmour et al.,¹⁸ which was used as a reference for model validation. These values were kept constant throughout all simulations to ensure consistency and comparability between our open-source model and the established reference framework.

The selected reactor length of 1.2 m was chosen to approximate the spatial scale of the gasifier used in the reference study,¹⁸ in which a Gibbs reactor was employed. Although the original study assumed thermodynamic equilibrium, our kinetic model aims to capture the spatial evolution of species along the reactor length, under nonequilibrium conditions.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the main results obtained with the developed model. First, it shows how the model was validated by comparing the simulated results to reference data. Then, a sensitivity analysis is included to evaluate the effect of two key operating variables: the air/steam ratio and the plasma preheating temperature.

3.1. Model Validation

The model was validated by comparing its results with experimental data from a study conducted by Nemmour et al.,¹⁸ which analyzed the syngas composition produced by the plasma gasification of municipal solid waste (See Tables 7, 8, and 9). Notably, Nemmour's simulation had been previously validated against three independent studies, reinforcing the reliability of reference data and providing additional confidence in the robustness of our model's predictive capabilities. To assess the accuracy of the model, we utilize three metrics commonly employed in modeling approaches: the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE⁶¹) by eq 3, the Root-mean-square error (RMSE⁶²) by eq 4, and the Log Accuracy Ratio Squared⁶³ by eq 5. We set specific criteria, based on established research, to determine if the model accurately calculates the essential parameters in the output of each developed module. The model is deemed adequate if it meets the following thresholds: MAPE < 14.25%,⁶⁴ RMSE < 0.15,^{59,65} and Log Accuracy Ratio Squared < 0.2.⁶³

Table 7. MOD-1 Validation (Mixed Substream)

Description (Mole fraction)	MSW3_Model	MSW3_Real ¹⁸	$\frac{y_{\text{model}} - y_{\text{real}}}{y_{\text{real}}}$		[ln Q] ²
			y_{real}	$y_{\text{model}} - y_{\text{real}}$	
H ₂	0.6579	0.6579	0	0	0
O ₂	0.2089	0.2088	0.0004	1×10^{-8}	2.29×10^{-7}
N ₂	0.0111	0.0111	0	0	0
S	0.0024	0.0023	0.0434	1×10^{-8}	0.0018
H ₂ O	0.1149	0.1140	0.0078	8.1×10^{-7}	6.18×10^{-5}
			MAPE	RMSE	Σ
			1.04%	0.0004	0.0018

Table 8. MOD-2 Validation (Mixed Substream)

Description (Mole fraction)	Plasma_Model	Plasma_Real ¹⁸	$\frac{y_{\text{model}} - y_{\text{real}}}{y_{\text{real}}}$		[ln Q] ²
			y_{real}	$y_{\text{model}} - y_{\text{real}}$	
O ₂	0.06917	0.06917	0	0	0
N ₂	0.3151	0.3151	0	0	0
H ₂ O	0.6157	0.6157	0	0	0
			MAPE	RMSE	Σ
			1.04%	0.0004	0.0018

Table 9. MOD-3 Validation (Mixed Substream)

Description (Mole fraction)	Syngas_Model	Syngas_Real ¹⁸	$\frac{y_{\text{model}} - y_{\text{real}}}{y_{\text{real}}}$		[ln Q] ²
			y_{real}	$y_{\text{model}} - y_{\text{real}}$	
H ₂	0.4431	0.4142	0.0770	0.0008	0
O ₂	0.0001	0.0001	0	0.0000	0.0902
N ₂	0.097	0.1283	0.2595	0.0010	0.0064
CO	0.1822	0.1974	0.0770	0.0002	0.0244
CO ₂	0.1272	0.1088	0.01691	0.0003	0.0656
H ₂ O	0.1482	0.1147	0.2920	0.0011	0.0001
			MAPE	RMSE	Σ
			14.19	0.0241	0.1792

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{100\%}{n} \times \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{y_{\text{model}} - y_{\text{real}}}{y_{\text{real}}} \right| \quad (3)$$

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y_{\text{model}} - y_{\text{real}}}{n}} \quad (4)$$

$$\sum [\ln Q]^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{y_{\text{model}}}{y_{\text{real}}} \right]^2 \quad (5)$$

The analysis in Tables 7–9 demonstrates that our developed model exhibits strong adequacy and predictive capability for syngas production through gasification processes. MOD-1 showed excellent agreement between the determined values and reference values with a Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) of 1.04%, a Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of 0.0004, and a Log Accuracy Ratio Squared (LARS) of 0.0018. These results confirm that the model accurately approximates stoichiometric transformations and characterizes biomass effectively.

For MOD-2, the MAPE, RMSE, and LARS values were 0, indicating an adequate representation of the air-steam mixture entering the gasification reactor. In contrast, for MOD-3, the RMSE = 0.0241 and LARS = 0.1792 indicators are below the established validation limits, which were 0.15 and 0.2, respectively. However, the MAPE value (14.19%) is close to the threshold established at <14.25%. This value is attributed to deviations in the prediction of the N₂ and H₂O

concentrations. MOD-3 underestimates N₂ by 25.95% and overestimates H₂O by 29.20%; these differences can be attributed to the modeling approaches used.

Our model uses a plug-flow reactor (PFR) with kinetic parameters considering oxidation and reduction reactions, while the reference study¹⁸ used a Gibbs-R reactor, which assumes overall thermodynamic equilibrium for all species. Gibbs-R tends to overestimate thermodynamically favored species (such as CO₂ and H₂O) and underestimate kinetically limited or unreactive species (such as residual N₂). PFR provides a more approximate model of in situ gasification behavior, especially under nonequilibrium and high-temperature conditions, where reaction kinetics predominate.³¹ Kinetic models allow the explicit simulation of reaction rates and the influence of activation energy barriers, features not taken into account in equilibrium models. Feng et al.⁶⁶ demonstrated the kinetic models provide significantly superior agreement with experimental syngas compositions compared to equilibrium-based approaches. Moreover, the PFR is scalable, meaning that the model can be easily adapted to larger or smaller reactor sizes by modification of its length or diameter.

Despite these differences in MOD-3, the model showed accurate predictions for H₂ and CO, the main energy carriers of syngas, with relative errors of 8.0% and 6.9%, respectively. CO₂ also showed a minimal deviation of 1.69%, which is within acceptable limits. Therefore, the fact that the overall MAPE is close to the threshold, while the RMSE and ln Q² remain low, reinforces the idea that our model is a reliable and

Figure 2. Concentration profile: syngas composition.

robust tool for evaluating the synthesis gas composition in a gasification process using an air/steam mixture as a gasifying agent.

As a result, it is a more reliable analytical tool for analyzing gasification processes under conditions that better simulate real-world operating parameters. The complete model is detailed in the Technical User Guide (SI: Appendix II).

The developed model constitutes a solid foundation for the kinetic modeling of plasma gasification. However, like any model, it has certain limitations. The model currently considers the reactor's adiabatic, isobaric, and steady state conditions and uses kinetic parameters from the literature. Furthermore, the reactor does not currently model the formation of trace species such as HCN or tars compounds. These byproducts, although typically present in small quantities, can significantly influence the overall syngas quality. For instance, the presence of tars may condense downstream, causing operational issues and requiring additional gas cleanup steps,⁶⁷ while nitrogenous species like HCN can affect the environmental performance of the syngas and necessitate further treatment.⁶⁸ From an energy perspective, the omission of tars can represent between 5% and 10% of the calorific value of raw feedstock, can reduce cold-gas efficiency when neglected, and can cause operational issues such as condensation and fouling in downstream equipment.⁶⁹ Similarly, the exclusion of species such as HCl and SO means that the model does not yet capture the formation of corrosive or toxic components that impact plant efficiency and equipment design.⁷⁰

Despite these simplifications, the results are significant and provide a starting point for future work and continuous improvement of the model. In future studies, we will adapt the model to account for nonideal and transient conditions that may affect the quality of the results, and we will calibrate the model's kinetics with in situ experimental data. Furthermore, the model considers reactions that include byproducts and

contaminants, making the model more complete, relevant, and applicable to industrial-scale gasification systems.

3.2. Syngas Production

Figure 2 illustrates the concentration profiles, expressed as molar fractions, of the main syngas components: CO, CO₂, H₂, O₂, and H₂O. These profiles show how the composition of syngas evolves with the length of the reactor. Notably, the H₂ content progressively increases, reaching its maximum concentration of 0.4461 at the outlet of the reactor. This increase is attributed to reactions that generate H₂, including carbon gasification (R1 - Reduction), the Water–Gas Shift (R4 - Reduction), and methane steam reforming (R6 - Reduction). These reactions enhance the energy content of the syngas and are favored by the high temperatures produced by the plasma, the high activation energies (1.5×10^5), and the consumption of O₂ in the initial stages, which creates a reducing environment. Moreover, the reduction in H₂O levels justifies the increase in the H₂ concentration, as H₂O is the primary reactant responsible for promoting H₂ formation.

In the first section of the reactor, O₂ is completely consumed, which promotes the oxidation of species and the formation of CO—a key component of syngas—and CO₂. CO is generated from the carbon oxidation reaction (R1 - Oxidation) and the partial oxidation of CH₄ (R2 - Oxidation), reaching a maximum concentration of 0.1822 at the reactor outlet. Meanwhile, in the middle and final zones of the reactor, CO is produced through carbon reduction (R1 - Reduction), the Boudouard reaction (R2 - Reduction), CO₂ reduction (R5 - Reduction), and methane reforming (R6 - Reduction). In contrast, CO₂ does not increase as significantly as CO because its main production sources are R1 and R4 of Oxidation. Since CO₂ formation depends on O₂, which is entirely consumed in the initial stage, and on H₂O (R4 - Reduction), which also decreases throughout the reactor, CO₂ is not produced in substantial amounts. At the reactor outlet, the concentration of CO₂ reaches a concentration of 0.1272.

Figure 3. Influence of ER on syngas composition at SFR = 0.

Figure 4. Influence of SFR on syngas composition at ER = 0.04.

The developed model, which considers Arrhenius-type kinetics, provides a more accurate approximation of the behavior of the chemical species involved in gasification. This model can be used to evaluate the impact of operating parameters on the quality of syngas, which can then be optimized for electricity generation and hydrogen production.

3.3. Sensitivity Analysis

Sensitivity analysis was performed to evaluate the influence of the air equivalence ratio (ER) and the steam-to-fuel ratio on syngas composition. The analyses were performed by varying the ER and SFR within typical operating ranges and holding all

other conditions constant to assess their influence on the main components (H₂, CO, CO₂, and CH₄) of the syngas.

3.3.1. Air Equivalence Ratio. The air equivalence ratio (ER) is defined as the ratio of the actual oxygen supplied to fuel compared with the amount of oxygen required for the complete combustion of theoretical biomass to fuel (eq 6). ER is a crucial parameter in gasification processes because it directly affects the composition of syngas and the overall efficiency of the process.^{71,72} Proper control of the ER is essential for optimizing the production of desired syngas components, such as hydrogen (H₂) and carbon monoxide (CO), as well as maximizing the energy conversion of biomass.

For our model, $\left(\frac{A}{F}\right)_{\text{Stoich}} = 7.62$ and it was calculated by the methodology proposed in a previous work.⁷³

$$\text{ER} = \frac{\left(\frac{A}{F}\right)_{\text{Actual}}}{\left(\frac{A}{F}\right)_{\text{Stoich}}} \quad (6)$$

A sensitivity analysis was conducted to assess how the equivalence ratio impacts syngas composition by varying the ER values between 0.04 and 0.16 in line with findings from other studies.^{18,74} To better isolate and evaluate the effect of the ER, the vapor stream was excluded, as this avoids interference from reactions with water (H₂O) that could distort the analysis of oxygen as an oxidizing agent.

Figure 3 shows the evolution of the concentration of the syngas components as a function of the ER (equivalence ratio) without considering the effect of the vapor stream on the plasma. It is observed that the mole fractions of CO and H₂ decrease to 0.145 and 0.324, respectively, with increasing ER, representing a reduction of 42.42% for CO and 25.67% for H₂. In contrast, the mole fraction of CO₂ increases from 0.148 to 0.288 (94.35% increase), while that of N₂ rises from 0.122 to 0.239 (95.90% increase). This increase in the CO₂ concentration is attributed to the increase in the ER ratio providing greater oxygen availability in the medium, favoring the CO oxidation reaction (R4 - Oxidation). As for H₂O, the absence of additional vapor input into the plasma stream limits its influence on the reduction reactions that typically promote H₂ formation, which partially explains the observed decrease in the concentration of this component. These results are consistent with previous research^{75–78} showing that an increase in ER reduces the energetic quality of syngas due to a decrease in the concentration of energetically valuable components (CO and H₂) and an increase in inert or undesirable compounds such as CO₂ and N₂.

3.3.2. Steam to Fuel Ratio (SFR). The SFR (steam to fuel ratio), defined as the ratio of the total mass of steam to the total mass of fuel (feedstock stream), is represented by eq 7 and is an important parameter because it influences syngas quality.^{79,80} To evaluate the influence of SFR on the final synthesis gas composition, we performed a sensitivity study by adjusting the SFE value between 0.04 and 1.3, consistent with the ranges reported in previous research.^{18,81} The analysis was performed with the ER value held constant at ER = 0.04 to assess the specific effects of steam on the syngas composition.

$$\text{SFR} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{steam}}}{\dot{m}_{\text{feedstock}}} \quad (7)$$

Figure 4 illustrates the evolution of syngas molar fractions as a function of the steam to fuel ratio (SFR). The data reveal an optimal SFR value of 0.08 at which hydrogen (H₂) concentration reaches its maximum (0.4552) due to steam gasification reactions (R1 - Reduction). However, beyond this threshold (SFR > 0.08), the H₂ fraction begins to decrease, which can be attributed to excess steam in the reaction environment. This suggests the existence of a critical threshold beyond which additional steam flow dilutes the syngas, limiting carbon conversion, reducing H₂ production, and consequently diminishing both the quality and energy efficiency of the produced syngas.

The carbon monoxide (CO) fraction significantly decreased from 0.27 to 0.127, resulting from syngas dilution. These

findings align with similar studies in the literature,^{82,83} which indicate that increasing SFR enhances H₂ production up to a certain point, after which H₂ concentration either plateaus or declines.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents one of the first plasma gasification models for municipal solid waste and developed open source using Python as the programming language. The proposal includes a modular system structure in three blocks (biomass decomposition, gasifying agent mixing, and plug flow reactor), allowing for a detailed simulation of the thermochemical process.

The model was validated by comparing the results with simulations performed on commercial platforms such as Aspen Plus, using error metrics such as RMSE, MAPE, and $\ln Q^2$, demonstrating the model's validity and robustness. Although the MAPE error value for MOD-3 is close to the validation threshold, the model demonstrates low errors in the key metrics of RMSE (0.0241) and $\ln Q^2$ (0.1792), which establishes its predictive capability and makes it a reliable tool for gasification analysis. Notably, the kinetic model incorporates oxidation and reduction reactions of biomass, resolving concentration profiles along the reactor, and thus provides a more realistic alternative to equilibrium-based models, such as the Gibbs-R. As supported by literature, this kinetic approach better reflects syngas formation under high-temperature, nonequilibrium conditions.

Sensitivity analysis showed that the air equivalence ratio (ER) and steam/fuel ratio (SFR) significantly influence syngas quality. The existence of an optimal SFR value suggests that excess steam can dilute the synthesis gas and reduce its energy content. Furthermore, high RE values tend to decrease the mole fractions of H₂ and CO in favor of CO₂ and N₂, which negatively affects the energy efficiency of the process.

The model's strength lies in its contribution as an open-source tool for analyzing gasification processes at the industrial and/or educational levels. The model can be adapted to various operating conditions including reactor geometry, biomass composition, reaction kinetics, and others. Furthermore, it promotes open science and continuous improvement in the analysis of gasification systems, breaking the barrier and reducing dependence on commercial software such as Aspen Plus.

Nevertheless, several limitations must be acknowledged. The current model assumes steady-state and adiabatic operation. It also relies on kinetic constants from the literature, which may not fully represent real-world feedstock variability or scale effects. Uncertainty arises mainly from the compositional heterogeneity of MSW, tar estimation, and extrapolation of kinetic parameters. Calibration with experimental data is needed for a greater accuracy.

In the industrial sector, the challenges include integration with gas cleaning systems, waste management, such as ash, and integration with real-time control and monitoring systems. Not all industries have the appropriate instrumentation for data analysis aimed at process optimization.

Despite these challenges, this model can be adapted to small- or large-scale geometries, different waste types, oxidation and reduction reactions, gasifying agents, and other factors, allowing for its transfer to other waste-to-energy systems such as pyrolysis and/or combustion.

This open-source code promotes transparency and scientific advancement, providing a foundation for continuous improvement of gasification kinetic models. In future work, we plan to calibrate the model with real in situ data focused on municipal solid waste and incorporate energy losses, byproducts, and pollutant analysis into the model, thereby enabling the model to predict syngas components, calorific value, and byproducts more accurately. In addition, genetic algorithms will be implemented to maximize the production of valuable synthesis gas components (H_2 and CO), process energy efficiency, and minimize unwanted byproducts (CO_2 and unconverted carbon) based on operating parameters such as biomass variability, reactor temperature, equivalence ratio (ER), steam-to-fuel ratio, and others. System optimization will contribute to the sustainability and adaptability of gasification systems for heterogeneous waste streams.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

SI Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acseengineeringau.5c00047>.

Thermodynamic equations and Python scripts for modeling biomass gasification and plasma-assisted reactions (PDF)

■ AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Authors

Daniel Chuquín-Vasco – Project Management, Innovation and Sustainability Research Center (PRINS), Universitat Politècnica de València, 03690 Alcoy, Spain; Safety and Resources Valorization Research Group (INVAGRO), Universidad Nacional de Chimborazo (UNACH), 060108 Riobamba, Ecuador; orcid.org/0000-0001-9637-3140; Email: dachuvas@upv.edu.es

Vanesa G. Lo-Iacono-Ferreira – Project Management, Innovation and Sustainability Research Center (PRINS), Universitat Politècnica de València, 03690 Alcoy, Spain; orcid.org/0000-0002-1411-8785; Email: valoia@upv.edu.es

Author

Juan I. Torregrosa-López – Project Management, Innovation and Sustainability Research Center (PRINS), Universitat Politècnica de València, 03690 Alcoy, Spain; orcid.org/0000-0001-7722-895X

Complete contact information is available at: <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acseengineeringau.5c00047>

Author Contributions

CRedit: **Daniel Chuquín-Vasco** conceptualization, methodology, software, validation, investigation, writing – original draft; **Vanesa G. Lo-Iacono-Ferreira** conceptualization, validation, formal analysis, writing – review and editing, visualization, supervision, funding acquisition; **Juan I. Torregrosa-López** conceptualization, validation, formal analysis, writing – review and editing, visualization.

Funding

Funding for open access charge: CRUE-Universitat Politècnica de València.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

■ ABBREVIATIONS

Latin

A	Pre-exponential factor in Arrhenius equation, varies (e.g., 1/s)
A/F	Air-to-Fuel ratio
c_i	Concentration of species i , kmol/m ³
E	Activation energy, kJ/kmol
\dot{m}	Mass flow, kg/s
r	Reaction rate, mol/m ³ ·s
R	Universal gas constant, 8.314 J/mol·K
y_{model}	Model value of the analyzed variable
y_{real}	Real/Experimental value of the analyzed variable

List of Abbreviations

ER	Equivalence Ratio (air-to-fuel ratio relative to stoichiometric combustion)
FT	Fischer–Tropsch
LARS	Log Accuracy Ratio Squared
MAPE	Mean Absolute Percentage Error
MSW	Municipal Solid Waste
MOD-1	Module 1: Biomass Decomposition
MOD-2	Module 2: Gasifying Agent (Plasma Stream)
MOD-3	Module 3: Gasification Reactor (Kinetic Modeling)
OSS	Open-Source Software
PFR	Plug-Flow Reactor
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SFR	Steam-to-Fuel Ratio
R#	Reaction Number (e.g., R1, R2, etc.)

■ REFERENCES

- Hagg, A.; Kirschner, K. N. Open-Source Machine Learning in Computational Chemistry. *J. Chem. Inf. Model.* **2023**, *63* (15), 4505–4532.
- Cummings, P. T.; Gilmer, J. B. Open-Source Molecular Modeling Software in Chemical Engineering. *Curr. Opin. Chem. Eng.* **2019**, *23*, 99–105.
- Klimt, J.; Eiling, N.; Wege, F.; Baude, J.; Monti, A. The Role of Open-Source Software in the Energy Sector. *Energies (Basel)* **2023**, *16* (16), 5855.
- Abeledo, P. R. *Digitalisation of Energy Action Plan: Linux Foundation Energy Response to European Commission Public Consultation*; DG ENER.B5; 2022.
- Faez, S.; Barnier, V.; Mentis, D. The Pivotal Role of Open Source Knowledge Transfer to Achieve Universal Energy Access. *iScience* **2025**, *28* (3), No. 112093.
- Liu, Z.; Luo, H.; Zhang, Y.; Luo, T.; Yang, X. A Review of Simulation Software for Energy Systems: Design, Functionality, and Applications. *Thermal Science and Engineering Progress* **2024**, *53*, No. 102760.
- Pandey, S.; Srivastava, V. C.; Kumar, V. High-Ash Low-Rank Coal Gasification: Process Modeling and Multiobjective Optimization. *ACS Engineering Au* **2023**, *3* (2), 59–75.
- Tewari, K.; Balyan, S.; Jiang, C.; Robinson, B.; Bhattacharyya, D.; Hu, J. Unlocking Syngas Synthesis from the Catalytic Gasification of Lignocellulose Pinewood: Catalytic and Pressure Insights. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2024**, *12* (11), 4718–4730.
- Mohapatra, S. S.; Singh, R. K. Production and Characterization of the Maximum Liquid Product Obtained from Co-Pyrolysis of Sugarcane Bagasse and Thermocol Waste. *Cellulose* **2021**, *28* (7), 4223–4239.

- (10) Zhang, Y.; Hou, D.; Sun, X.; Zhu, X.; Yan, B.; Chen, G. Different Pretreatment of Biomass for Gasification: A Critical Review. *Journal of the Energy Institute* **2025**, *119*, No. 101992.
- (11) Maier, M.; Schulze-Netzer, C.; Adams, T. A. Chemical Recycling of Plastic Waste via Production of Ethylene from Gasification Syngas. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **2025**, *64*, 575.
- (12) Ruiz, M. P.; Faria, J. A. Catalysis at the Solid–Liquid–Liquid Interface of Water–Oil Pickering Emulsions: A Tutorial Review. *ACS Engineering Au* **2022**, *2* (4), 295–319.
- (13) Rey, J. R. C.; Longo, A.; Rijo, B.; Pedrero, C. M.; Tarelho, L. A. C.; Brito, P. S. D.; Nobre, C. A Review of Cleaning Technologies for Biomass-Derived Syngas. *Fuel* **2024**, *377*, No. 132776.
- (14) Hos, T.; Herskowitz, M. Techno-Economic Analysis of Biogas Conversion to Liquid Hydrocarbon Fuels through Production of Lean-Hydrogen Syngas. *ACS Engineering Au* **2022**, *2* (5), 450–460.
- (15) Gao, N.; Milandile, M. H.; Quan, C.; Rundong, L. Critical Assessment of Plasma Tar Reforming during Biomass Gasification: A Review on Advancement in Plasma Technology. *J. Hazard. Mater.* **2022**, *421*, 126764.
- (16) Zhao, Y.; Yao, J.; Chen, G.; Liu, J.; Cheng, Z.; Wang, L.; Yi, W.; Xu, S. Energy, Efficiency, and Environmental Analysis of Hydrogen Generation via Plasma Co-Gasification of Biomass and Plastics Based on Parameter Simulation Using Aspen Plus. *Energy Convers Manag* **2023**, *295*, 117623.
- (17) Yayalík, İ.; Koyun, A.; Akgün, M. Gasification of Municipal Solid Wastes in Plasma Arc Medium. *Plasma Chemistry and Plasma Processing* **2020**, *40* (6), 1401–1416.
- (18) Nemmour, A.; Inayat, A.; Janajreh, I.; Ghenai, C. Syngas Production from Municipal Solid Waste Plasma Gasification: A Simulation and Optimization Study. *Fuel* **2023**, *349*, 128698.
- (19) Aguilar-Virgen, Q.; Taboada-González, P. Comparison of Technologies for Waste Treatment with Energy Recovery: An Overview. *Waste* **2025**, *Vol. 3*, Page 10 **2025**, *3* (1), 10.
- (20) Mukherjee, C.; Denney, J.; Mbonimpa, E. G.; Slagley, J.; Bhowmik, R. A Review on Municipal Solid Waste-to-Energy Trends in the USA. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* **2020**, *119*, No. 109512.
- (21) Nagar, V.; Kaushal, R. A Review of Recent Advancement in Plasma Gasification: A Promising Solution for Waste Management and Energy Production. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2024**, *77*, 405–419.
- (22) Wang, S.; Shi, H.; Wang, P. Techno-Economic and Scalability Analysis of Nitrogen Plasma Gasification of Medical Waste. *Waste Management* **2025**, *198*, 55–65.
- (23) Anilkumar, R.; Vinayak, A. K.; Kiran, B.; Gurumoorthy, A. V. P. Study of Municipal Solid Waste Treatment Using Plasma Gasification by Application of Aspen Plus. *Chemical Product and Process Modeling* **2024**, *19* (6), 901–915.
- (24) Montiel-Bohórquez, N. D.; Agudelo, A. F.; Pérez, J. F. Modelling of an Integrated Plasma Gasification Combined Cycle Power Plant Using Aspen Plus. *Journal of King Saud University – Engineering Sciences* **2024**, *36*, 620–631.
- (25) Dhrioua, M.; Ghachem, K.; Hassen, W.; Ghazy, A.; Kolsi, L.; Borjini, M. N. Simulation of Biomass Air Gasification in a Bubbling Fluidized Bed Using Aspen Plus: A Comprehensive Model Including Tar Production. *ACS Omega* **2022**, *7* (37), 33518–33529.
- (26) Niu, M.; Huang, Y.; Jin, B.; Wang, X. Simulation of Syngas Production from Municipal Solid Waste Gasification in a Bubbling Fluidized Bed Using Aspen Plus. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **2013**, *52* (42), 14768–14775.
- (27) Vikram, S.; Rosha, P.; Kumar, S. Recent Modeling Approaches to Biomass Pyrolysis: A Review. *Energy Fuels* **2021**, *35* (9), 7406–7433.
- (28) Han, B.; Kumar, D.; Pei, Y.; Norton, M.; Adams, S. D.; Khoo, S. Y.; Kouzani, A. Z. Modelling of Thermochemical Processes of Waste Recycling: A Review. *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis* **2024**, *182*, No. 106687.
- (29) Cvetinović, D.; Erić, A.; Cvetković, S.; Komatina, M.; Manić, N.; Janković, B. Performance Assessment and Techno-Economic Analysis of the Thermal Plasma Gasification of Biomass Using Air and Steam as Gasification Medium. *Appl. Therm Eng.* **2025**, *276*, 126940.
- (30) Dossow, M.; Bastek, S.; Spliethoff, H.; Fendt, S. Electrifying Biomass-to-Liquid Processes Using Plasma-Assisted Entrained Flow Gasification. *Energy Convers Manag* **2025**, *341*, 120049.
- (31) Batista, C. T. N.; Mohammed, K. A.; Amiri, A.; Azimi, N.; Steinberger-Wilckens, R. Comparison of Equilibrium-Based and Kinetics-Based Models for Evaluating the Impact of Hydrogen Carrier Reforming on SOFC System. *Energy Convers Manag* **2025**, *332*, 119733.
- (32) Angikath, F.; Saxena, S.; Dryer, F.; Han, H.; Dally, B. A Novel Free Radical Mechanism Based Model for Predicting Gasification Metrics and Synergistic Interactions in Supercritical Water Gasification of Plastics. *Fuel* **2026**, *404*, 136182.
- (33) Python Software Foundation. *python*; <https://www.python.org/about/> (accessed 2025–04–09).
- (34) Mutlu, Ö. Ç.; Zeng, T. Challenges and Opportunities of Modeling Biomass Gasification in Aspen Plus: A Review. *Chem. Eng. Technol.* **2020**, *43* (9), 1674–1689.
- (35) Brinkmann, S.; Seyfang, B. C. Building a Code-Based Model to Describe Syngas Production from Biomass. *ChemEngineering* **2024**, *8* (5), 94.
- (36) Ayeni, A. O.; Oladokun, O.; Orodu, O. D., Eds. *Advanced Manufacturing in Biological, Petroleum, and Nanotechnology Processing; Green Energy and Technology*; Springer International Publishing: Cham, 2022; DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-95820-6.
- (37) Keniley, S.; Curreli, D. CRANE: A MOOSE-Based Open Source Tool for Plasma Chemistry Applications. *arXiv* **2019**, 1905.10004; DOI: 10.48550/arXiv.1905.10004.
- (38) Oliveira, M.; Ramos, A.; Ismail, T. M.; Monteiro, E.; Rouboa, A. A Review on Plasma Gasification of Solid Residues: Recent Advances and Developments. *Energies* **2022**, *Vol. 15*, Page 1475 **2022**, *15* (4), 1475.
- (39) Ferreira, S.; Monteiro, E.; Brito, P.; Vilarinho, C. A Holistic Review on Biomass Gasification Modified Equilibrium Models. *Energies* **2019**, *Vol. 12*, Page 160 **2019**, *12* (1), 160.
- (40) Project Jupyter. *Jupyter notebook*; <https://jupyter.org/> (accessed 2025–04–09).
- (41) Numpy Project. *NumPy*; <https://numpy.org/about/> (accessed 2025–04–09).
- (42) SciPy Project. *SciPy*; <https://scipy.org/> (accessed 2025–04–09).
- (43) Martin, C. *PYroMater*; <http://pyromat.org/about.html> (accessed 2025–04–09).
- (44) Bell, I. H.; Wronski, J.; Quoilin, S.; Lemort, V. Pure and Pseudo-Pure Fluid Thermophysical Property Evaluation and the Open-Source Thermophysical Property Library Coolprop. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **2014**, *53* (6), 2498–2508.
- (45) Grecco, H. E. *Pint: makes units easy*; <https://pint.readthedocs.io/en/stable/> (accessed 2025–04–09).
- (46) Jiang, W.; Tao, J.; Zhong, X.; Ye, Y.; Kang, J.; Tang, Q.; Liu, D.; Ren, Y.; Li, D.; Cai, H.; Li, D. Co-Gasification of Rural Solid Waste and Biomass in Rural Areas: Simulation and Plant-Scale Process. *Environ. Res.* **2023**, *235*, 116684.
- (47) Zhang, Y. M.; Li, J. L.; Wang, J. P.; Wang, B. Z. High Temperature Pyrolysis of Toluene under Electromagnetic Fields at Different Frequencies. *ACS Sustain Chem. Eng.* **2016**, *4* (9), 4573–4581.
- (48) Mehdi, M.; Ammar Taqvi, S. A.; Shaikh, A. A.; Khan, S.; Naqvi, S. R.; Shahbaz, M.; Juchelková, D. Aspen plus Simulation Model of Municipal Solid Waste Gasification of Metropolitan City for Syngas Production. *Fuel* **2023**, *344*, 128128.
- (49) Ondachi, P. A.; Ozigis, I. I.; Zarmai, M. T. Physicochemical Characterisation of Abuja’s Municipal Solid Wastes as a Renewable Energy Resource. *ABUAD Journal of Engineering Research and Development (AJERD)* **2023**, *6* (1), 38–43.
- (50) Niu, B.; Han, X.; Ding, J.; Yan, B.; Chen, G.; Yao, J. Energy, Efficiency, Economy, Environmental Assessment of Hydrogen Production via Solar-Driven Steam Gasification of Fresh Cow Manure Using Aspen Plus Simulation Model. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2025**, *98*, 308–320.

- (51) Vyazovkin, S. Power Law and Arrhenius Approaches to the Melting Kinetics of Superheated Crystals: Are They Compatible? *Cryst. Growth Des* **2018**, *18* (11), 6389–6392.
- (52) Zhu, D.; Wang, Q.; Zhang, Z.; Xie, G.; Luo, Zhongyang. Kinetics Simulation Study of Biomass Partial Gasification for Producer Gas and Biochar Co-Production in the Fluidized Bed. *Energy* **2025**, *318*, 134919.
- (53) Shahbaz, M.; Ammar, M.; Sukarni, S. Conversion of Spirulina Platensis into Methanol via Gasification: Process Simulation Modeling and Economic Evaluation. *Digital Chemical Engineering* **2025**, *14*, 100204.
- (54) Wei, P.; Chen, G.; Zhi, F.; Zhang, A.; Deng, H.; Wen, X.; Wang, F.; Yu, C. Numerical Simulation and Experimental Study of Hydrogen Production from Chili Straw Waste Gasification Using Aspen Plus. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2024**, *95*, 377–388.
- (55) Gao, K.; Chen, G.; Yan, B.; Ti, S.; Wang, H.; Si, G.; Qi, T. Modeling of Biomass Thermal Decomposition/Gasification in a Downdraft Gasifier under Low Pressure by Aspen Plus. *Thermal Science and Engineering Progress* **2025**, *59*, 103229.
- (56) Martínez Gonz alez, A.; Eduardo Silva Lora, E.; Carlos Escobar Palacio, J.; Agustín Almaz an del Olmo, O. Hydrogen Production from Oil Sludge Gasification/Biomass Mixtures and Potential Use in Hydrotreatment Processes. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* **2018**, *43*, 7808.
- (57) Zare, A. A. D.; Yari, M. Comprehensive Analysis of Energy, Exergy, and Economic Aspects in a Multi-Generation System: Power, Methanol, and Heat Generation through Plastic Waste Gasification. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2024**, *95*, 129–143.
- (58) Qi, J.; Liu, J.; Chen, G.; Yao, J.; Yan, B.; Yi, W.; Zao, H.; Xu, S. Hydrogen Production from Municipal Solid Waste via Chemical Looping Gasification Using CuFe₂O₄ Spinel as Oxygen Carrier: An Aspen Plus Modeling. *Energy Convers Manag* **2023**, *294*, 117562.
- (59) Njuguna, F.; Ndiritu, H.; Gathitu, B.; Hawi, M.; Munyalo, J. Kinetic Modeling and Optimization of Process Parameters for Gasification of Macadamia Nutshells with Air Preheating: A Combined Use of Aspen Plus and Response Surface Methodology (RSM). *Bioresour Technol. Rep* **2023**, *22*, 101477.
- (60) Rossetti, I.; Tripodi, A.; Tommasi, M.; Ramis, G. Conceptual Design of a Process for Hydrogen Production from Waste Biomass and Its Storage in Form of Liquid Ammonia. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2023**, *48* (96), 37443–37460.
- (61) Hung, C. Y.; Wang, C. C.; Lin, S. W.; Jiang, B. C. An Empirical Comparison of the Sales Forecasting Performance for Plastic Tray Manufacturing Using Missing Data. *Sustainability* **2022**, *Vol. 14*, Page 2382 **2022**, *14* (4), 2382.
- (62) Li, Z.; Bi, S.; Hao, S.; Cui, Y. Aboveground Biomass Estimation in Forests with Random Forest and Monte Carlo-Based Uncertainty Analysis. *Ecol Indic* **2022**, *142*, 109246.
- (63) Tofallis, C. A Better Measure of Relative Prediction Accuracy for Model Selection and Model Estimation. *Journal of the Operational Research Society* **2015**, *66* (8), 1352–1362.
- (64) Wang, L.; Zhang, Z.; Long, H.; Xu, J.; Liu, R. Wind Turbine Gearbox Failure Identification with Deep Neural Networks. *IEEE Trans Industr Inform* **2017**, *13* (3), 1360–1368.
- (65) Hussan, W.; Khurram Shahzad, M.; Seidel, F.; Nestmann, F. Application of Soft Computing Models with Input Vectors of Snow Cover Area in Addition to Hydro-Climatic Data to Predict the Sediment Loads. *Water (Switzerland)* **2020**, *12* (5), 1481.
- (66) Feng, L.; Zhang, G.; Zhai, R. Study on Gasification Reaction and Energy Conversion Characteristics of the Entrained Flow Coal Gasification Based on Chemical Kinetics Simulation. *Heliyon* **2024**, *10* (10), e30997.
- (67) Bhaduri, S.; Contino, F.; Jeanmart, H.; Breuer, E. The Effects of Biomass Syngas Composition, Moisture, Tar Loading and Operating Conditions on the Combustion of a Tar-Tolerant HCCI (Homogeneous Charge Compression Ignition) Engine. *Energy* **2015**, *87*, 289–302.
- (68) Paterson, N.; Zhuo, Y.; Dugwell, D.; Kandiyoti, R. Formation of Hydrogen Cyanide and Ammonia during the Gasification of Sewage Sludge and Bituminous Coal. *Energy Fuels* **2005**, *19* (3), 1016–1022.
- (69) Liu, Z. Gasification of Municipal Solid Wastes: A Review on the Tar Yields. *Energy Sources, Part A: Recovery, Utilization and Environmental Effects* **2019**, *41* (11), 1296–1304.
- (70) Zhang, H.; Yu, S.; Shao, L.; He, P. Estimating Source Strengths of HCl and SO₂ Emissions in the Flue Gas from Waste Incineration. *J. Environ. Sci. (China)* **2019**, *75*, 370–377.
- (71) Campoy, M.; Gómez-Barea, A.; Villanueva, A. L.; Ollero, P. Air-Steam Gasification of Biomass in a Fluidized Bed under Simulated Autothermal and Adiabatic Conditions. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **2008**, *47* (16), 5957–5965.
- (72) Zhang, B.; Tian, Z.; Wang, Q.; Ma, D.; Jia, R. Investigation on the Impact of Air Equivalence Ratio on the Characteristics of Lignite Coal Partial Gasification Products in Fluidized Bed. *Journal of the Energy Institute* **2025**, *119*, No. 102008.
- (73) Nemmour, A.; Inayat, A.; Janajreh, I.; Ghenai, C. New Performance Correlations of Municipal Solid Waste Gasification for Sustainable Syngas Fuel Production. *Biomass Convers Biorefin* **2022**, *12* (10), 4271–4289.
- (74) Li, H.; Li, T.; Wei, X. Main Performance Analysis of Kitchen Waste Gasification in a Small-Power Horizontal Plasma Jet Reactor. *Journal of the Energy Institute* **2020**, *93* (1), 367–376.
- (75) Jamin, N. A.; Saleh, S.; Fazli, A.; Samad, A. Influences of Gasification Temperature and Equivalence Ratio on Fluidized Bed Gasification of Raw and Torrefied Wood Wastes. *Chem. Eng. Trans* **2020**, *80*, 127.
- (76) Vaezi, M.; Passandideh-Fard, M.; Moghiman, M.; Charmchi, M. Gasification of Heavy Fuel Oils: A Thermochemical Equilibrium Approach. *Fuel* **2011**, *90* (2), 878–885.
- (77) Gao, Y.; Wang, M.; Raheem, A.; Wang, F.; Wei, J.; Xu, D.; Song, X.; Bao, W.; Huang, A.; Zhang, S.; Zhang, H. Syngas Production from Biomass Gasification: Influences of Feedstock Properties, Reactor Type, and Reaction Parameters. *ACS Omega* **2023**, *8* (35), 31620–31631.
- (78) Ali, M.; Mahmood, F.; Magoua Mbeugang, C.; Kumar, S.; Tang, J.; Li, B. Synthesis of Syngas from Municipal Solid Waste in a Fluidized Bed Gasifier. *Thermal Science* **2024**, *28*, 3647.
- (79) Choi, Y. K.; Cho, M. H.; Kim, J. S. Steam/Oxygen Gasification of Dried Sewage Sludge in a Two-Stage Gasifier: Effects of the Steam to Fuel Ratio and Ash of the Activated Carbon on the Production of Hydrogen and Tar Removal. *Energy* **2015**, *91*, 160–167.
- (80) Zhang, H.; Yan, J.; Liu, J.; Wen, H.; Xiong, H.; Sun, K.; Gong, X.; Zhang, Y. Thermodynamic Modeling of Entrained-Flow Gasification of Solid Fuels Covering Biomass and Coal Categories: Model Simplification, Validation, and Application. *Journal of the Energy Institute* **2025**, *120*, No. 102086.
- (81) Mehrabian, M.; Mahmoudimehr, J. A Correlation for Optimal Steam-to-Fuel Ratio in a Biogas-Fueled Solid Oxide Fuel Cell with Internal Steam Reforming by Using Artificial Neural Networks. *Renew Energy* **2023**, *219*, No. 119397.
- (82) Bourguig, O.; Ramos, A.; Bouziane, K.; Asbik, M.; Monteiro, E.; Rouboa, A. Performance Assessment of the Co-Gasification for Sustainable Management of Municipal Solid Waste: Moroccan Case. *Energy Reports* **2022**, *8*, 1530–1540.
- (83) Safarian, S.; Unnthorsson, R.; Richter, C. Performance Investigation of Biomass Gasification for Syngas and Hydrogen Production Using Aspen Plus. *Open Journal of Modelling and Simulation* **2022**, *10*, 71–87.